

The Multiple Lineages of 'Khetauris': A Forgotten Chapter in the History of Santhal Parganas

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Summary :

Khetauri kings and *zamindars* have left behind valuable historical treasures in the form of remains and material objects. But due to negligence and lack of proper care their conditions are fast deteriorating day by day. If proper maintenance and care is not taken then, the day is not far when they would fade into oblivion. Khetauris were always part of the local setup of Santhal Pargana and behaved in a manner which suited them most at a given point of time. They asserted Kshatriya *Varna* like status by self proclamation of *Suryavanshi* Kshatriya during medieval period, as Man Singh was overseeing the operations of Santhal Pargana area. Things have changed afterward; Khetauris were called tribal by British Raj dispensation in the first half of twentieth century and got included in the Backward Community List by the then Bihar Government of Independent India. Lately, not satisfied with backward tag due to under-development of the community, Khetauris have started demanding tribal status. Their history is a rich example of the contingencies of identity formation in modern India.

Key words: Santhal Pargana, Report, Khetauri, Ghatwal, Property

Preface :

Khetauri is a culturally distinct group of people residing in different areas of Santhal Pargana. Khetauris are one of the early occupants of the region, earlier called *Damin-i-koh*, after ancient groups of *Paharias* and *Bhuiyas*. Khetauris were rulers of different regions of Santhal Pargana and adjoining areas from sixteenth century onwards. They held *Mansab* and *Jagir* titles accorded to them by the Mughals. Khetauris even adopted Fasli chronological system in maintaining calendar years, which was devised by Emperor Akbar for land revenue purpose in Northern India. This article attempts to outline the contours for constructing a tentative history of Khetauris in Santhal Parganas so that understanding about Khetauris could be augmented.

Research Methodology:

In-depth study and analysis of historical dimensions have been done under the analytical and descriptive method for the study of the presented research "Many genealogies of 'Khetauri': A forgotten chapter in the history of Santhal Pargana".

Research Objective:

The purpose of the presented research article is to study the many genealogies of 'Khetauri': a forgotten one in the history of Santhal Pargana and to bring new facts to the fore through this research.

Hypothesis:

Many genealogies of 'Khetauri': A forgotten chapter in the history of Santhal Pargana, what has been the importance of these facts.

Main proposition:

In fact Man Singh, a viceroy of Akbar, finds little prospects of directly obtaining revenue from the hills of *Paharias* had given control of the region to different Khetauri families as a reward for their support to his conquests of Bengal. The descendants of Khetauri *Mansabdars* ruled from

Rajmahal and Pakur on the east of the hills to Colgong (Kahalgaon) and Godda on the western side. Some descendants even received the title of 'Raja'. Khetauris withstood ups and downs of time, but their lives have undergone dramatic change after independence of the country. Except for a handful of direct descendants of different estate rulers, others have a difficult time. Their number was recorded as 1,431 in 1901, 27,024 in 1911, 20,946 in 1921, 26,787 in 1931 and 20,702 in 1941. The number of Khetauris at the census of 1901 was returned as only 1,431, but the similarity of the name with Kshatriya and the claim of the Khetauris to be Kshatriya have, it is believed led to them being, regarded as Rajputs in many cases.²

The general impression about Khetauris is that they were basically warriors who lived by swords and conquests. There are lot of speculations about and legends woven around them. To some they were tribal Rajas and to many others they were akin to Rajput rulers.

I

Eminent scholars, including historians have not widely studied the Khetauris, and have not adequately portrayed them. Even very recent publications do not refer to the Khetauris of Santhal Parganas, though they form an important and culturally distinct group residing in the districts of Sahibganj, Dumka and Godda of Santhal Pargana. It appears that their significance in historical perspective has not been properly considered so far. Khetauris of Santhal Parganas could have been well studied by various suitable approaches, but there is none. Whatever sketch one makes of Khetauris is by reading sporadic references of Khetauris in different District Gazetteers, Journals, Census Reports, Survey and Settlement Reports, etc.

Perhaps Francis Buchanan was the first British ethnographer who wrote on Khetauris in his book,

*An Account of the District of Bhagalpur in 1810-11.*¹ In fact Francis Buchanan has presented a mystified picture of Khetauris emergence in Delhi who were forced by circumstances to move to Kharagpur and then to Chotanagpur. In the first decade of 20th century, H. McPherson was the first scholar who broadly wrote on Khetauris in his works, *Aboriginal Races of Sonthal Parganas* published in 1908 and *Final Report on the Survey and Settlement Operations in the District of Sonthal Parganas* published in 1909. L.S.S. O'Malley also wrote in detail about the tribes and castes of Santhal Parganas in his works, *Bengal District Gazetteers: Santal Parganas*² published in 1910 and *Bihar and Orissa District Gazetteers: Monghyr*³ published in 1926. O'Malley has made a mention of Khetauri estates under the titles, 'History', 'The People' and 'Gazetteer'. Even this mention is passing, very scattered and does not even properly enumerate the number of estates held by Khetauris.

Rai Bahadur S.C. Mukherjee in his work, *Bihar District Gazetteers: Santal Parganas* published in 1938, which is a revised edition of the *Bengal District Gazetteers: Santal Parganas* of L.S.S. O'Malley has nothing more to offer except putting the Khetauris and Bhuiyas under Semi-Tribals. P.C. Roy Choudhary's *Gazetteers entitled Bihar District Gazetteers: Bhagalpur*⁴ published in 1962 and *Bihar District Gazetteers: Santhal Parganas* published in 1965, were in line with the previous Gazetteers, except that it shows the numerical strength of Khetauris and Bhuiyas, from 1901 to 1941. Khetnuri' population figure has been shown under 'Selected Tribes' in the census of 1941.

Apart from the above mentioned works on Khetauris, one also get their references and partial past history from various other local booklet and leaflet publications. Thus, the published references pertaining to the Khetauris are very marginal, absolutely sketchy and lack in any depth. The few brief booklets that deal with them portray royal past of the Khetauris but without proper references. Khetauri saga has been in fact severely underreported and carries very little written work. Many of these are in long narrative and local traditions covered by British administrators in Gazetteers as well as Survey and Settlement records. Thus there is absolutely no comprehensive information on the Khetauris. The study had limitations like non-availability of proper secondary source data and that the present study was confined to past five hundred years and not beyond. The racial elements of Khetauris have not been touched in the present work.

The division of Santhal Parganas, earlier called Damin-i-koh and present day commissionaire of newly created Jharkhand state, lies between 23°40' and 25°18' north latitude and between 86°28'

and 87°57' east longitude. It contains a population of 45,71,658 as ascertained by the census of 1991 and it extends over 5470 sq. miles. Dumka is the administrative headquarters of Santhal Pargana. Santhal Parganas is bounded on the north by the districts of Bhagalpur, Purnea; on the east by Malda, Murshidabad and Birbhum; on the south by Burdwan and Dhanbad; and on the west by Hagaribagh, Munger and Bhagalpur. The boundary on the north and east is defined for some distance by the river Ganga, which separate Santhal Pargana from Purnea and Malda, while portions of the southern coincide with the Barakar and Ajai rivers which separate it from Dhabad and Burdwan.⁵ It is, "an upland tract with a hilly backbone running from north to south. To the north and east it is flanked by a long but narrow strip of alluvial soil hemmed in between the river Ganges and the Rajmahal Hills."⁶

Moreover, Khetauris who number a little more than a lakh in Santhal Parganas are concentrated in a number of villages of three districts of Santhal Parganas ie Godda, Sahibganj and Dumka

Field work conducted in Khetauri dominated villages of Santhal Parganas and in the remains of Khetauri estates and religious centres suggest an interesting interplay of tradition and modernity. Primary source techniques like free flowing interview, interview schedule, observation and investigation reveal that the Khetauris are still a thriving community. Extensive library and archive work was done to collect information of Khetauris. Survey and Settlement Reports such as of McPherson, Gantzer; District Gazetteers of Santhal Parganas, Bhagalpur and Munger, Old Journals of English administrator Buchanan; Numerous Research Articles, Decennial Census Reports and Court Accounts like that of Dumka's Deputy Commissioner Boxwell Esquire were studied in order to understand the place of Khetauris in the historical records.

II

Khetauris are considered to be one of the earliest settlers of Santhal Pargana like the Paharias and the Bhuiyas. O'Malley confirms this when he says that an early occupant of the district, Bhuiyas owed allegiance to the Khetauris who had their chief seat at Kharagpur and exercised supremacy. They were ruled over by fifty- two chiefs until they were overcome by Rajput adventurers from north India.⁵ Besides, the above mentioned chief estates of the Khetauris, there are also references of a number of big and small estates which were dominated by the Khetauris in their history of past 500 years. The Khetauri chiefs built many forts in this region.

Quite interestingly, folktales and stories have inherited great significance among the

Khetauris since long. These tales provide certain glimpses of their historical and cultural antecedents. Among many popular folktales it is believed that Khetauris were in existence even during the time of *Parsurama*, the mythological god. They say that it was the beginning of their losing out from the mainstream. The timing of the myth thus specifies their existence as 7500 years old. Buchanan cites another folktale related to the expulsion of Khetauris from Kharagpur and says that three brothers, Dandu, Vasudev and Mahindra of the Kinawar tribe of Rajputs, took service and became favourites of Sasanka, the Khetauri Raja of Kharagpur. During a friendly intercourse, they had an opportunity of perceiving how his house might be attacked; and one night in the year 1503 A.D., having collected a band of Rajputs, they suddenly attacked the house and put the Raja to death. Dandu immediately proclaimed Raja by beat of drum, and from time to time destroyed other Khetari chiefs who had depended on Sasanka, and seized on their estates.⁷

It could be said that Khetauris' power struggle in Santhal Parganas was unique in a sense that they acquired power and estate with sheer diligence and shrewdness. Khetauris utilized every opportunity to overthrow ruling masters of Santhal Pargana of that time. Mughal support consolidated and legitimized their position and made them the focal point of governance in Santhal Pargana. Khetauris' ascension to power in Santhal Pargana mystified their general rank and file. Power established Khetauris as martial race and their position were further strengthened during the British period, at the time of Permanent Settlement of Cornwallis. They were designated as 'Zamindars' and acted as intermediaries between the farmers and the British Government. However, the British Government took full advantage of their internal rifts and counter claims to seat of power, leading to their destabilisation. At the same time *Khetauris* also had to face the growing hostilities of the native Malers.

III

On exodus from Kharagpur's seat of power, Khetauris worked hard to gain position of power in Santhal Parganas, and are the only rulers of Santhal Parganas whose power game is explicitly recorded. Barkop, Patsunda, Manihari, Handwe, Usila etc., were some of the important estates of Khetauris in this region. A number of ruins consisting of their forts, temples, kutcheries, platforms, etc. could be found scattered here and there in these estates.

Barkop was formerly held by Nat Rajas, but during the reign of Akbar came into the possession of Deb Brahm, a Khetauri chief of Kharagpur, who settled in Patsunda having obtained a grant of Patsunda and Barkop from the Mughal Viceroy. In 1687 the estate was divided between two of his

descendants, Mani Brahm retaining Barkop, while Patsunda was handed over to his younger brother, Chandra Brahm. The headquarters of the Handwe Estate are at Nonihat, two miles from which under the Lagwa hill is the ancestral home of the Khetauri Rajas. Handwe was another of the *ghatwalis* of Kharagpur Raj. The first Khetauri *ghatwal* was Vijay Singh and it appears that the acquisition of Handwe by Vijay Singh was one of the sequels to the Rajput invasion of Kharagpur. According to McPherson, Manihari Estate was acquired by an inferior family of Khetauris led by Rupkaran. Man Singh conferred the title of 'Raja' on him and he enjoyed the estate till 1608 A.D.⁸

From their early days Khetauris were great warriors. They were men of great courage and valour and were known for their prowess. They were expert in war great tactics and had control over a wide range of armories to support them. The king's army consisted of the infantry, cavalry and elephants in general. Artistry has been in their blood. They were considered fine horse-riders and elephant-riders and had expertise in the art of sword-fighting, moving *bana*, archery, using *latthi*, etc.

IV

This part is devoted to later day Rajas and *zamindars* as well as lives and times of present day elites. In the early 19th century, according to Buchanan, the Khetauris there were above three thousand families in the middle parts of Santhal Parganas. In the division of Banka four of them assumed the dignity of kingdom, and took their titles from Manihari, Handwe, Barkop and Patsunda.⁹

Deb Brahm is considered to be the founder of the Khetauri family in Santhal Parganas and he held the joint estates of Patsunda and Barkop till they were separated in 1687 A.D. Deb Brahm was succeeded by his son Amar Brahm and Amar by his son Tilak. In 1687 A.D. the estate was divided between two of his descendants, Mani Brahm who retained Barkop while Patsunda was handed over to his younger brother Chandra Brahm. The proprietor at the time of the Permanent Settlement was Ajit Brahm who died in 1835 A.D. without any male issue, leaving two widows, Lilabati and Bhulanbati. The nature of the proprietors of the estates was that of an agent of the British Empire. They collected rent on behalf of the British Government.

A part of the revenue was given to them as a commission for the maintenance of their estates. After the death of Lilabati, Bhulanbati adopted Chandra Dayal Brahm, of the Patsunda family. She died shortly afterwards, and the estate came under the Court of Wards. Later the estate got encumbered with debt, and half of it was alienated by sale. A dispute between the adopted son and the sons of Lilabati's daughters resulted in the division of the Estate.¹⁰ After 1876 during the *British Raj* days

Barkop estate was transferred into a *Zamindari*. Babu Ram Charan Singh, Babu Guru Charan Singh and Babu Maha Prasad Singh were some of the early zamindars followed by Vidyanand Singh, Shashi Bhusan Singh and Radha Raman Singh. In 1962 A.D. all the properties of Radha Raman Singh was annexed by the Government and his *zamindari* was abolished.

On the other hand Chandra, who received *tappa* of Patsunda, was followed in regular succession, from father to son, by Gaj, Dular, Sital, Futeh, Tej, Tilak and Thakur Brahm. The estate was eventually sold up in January 1904 for debt and purchased by some *mahajans* of Bhagalpur. Finally it was been taken over by the Government of Bihar. Shri Shyam Lal Brahm is the tenth generation descendant of Chandra Brahm and a well known social worker. Kunwar Bateshwar Singh was a well known social worker, leader and politician who fought Assembly elections four times from Mahagama and Jarmundi. Kunwar Gopal Singh, son of late Kunwar Bateshwar Singh, is also a well known social worker, leader and politician.

Meanwhile, in the Handwe Estate Vijay Singh was succeeded by his eldest son Uday Singh followed by Puran, Tilak, Dalel, Sobha, Purandar, Jhabban, Madho and Udit. Udit died issueless and was succeeded by his wife Rani Kesobati Kumari, who adopted Kumar Satya Narayan Singh of the Barkop family as her heir. After the death of Satya Narayan Singh in 1924, he was succeeded by his wife Srimati Sonabati Kumari as the *ghatwalin* of the estate. The application of Bihar Land Reforms Act to *ghatwal* estate of Handwe was declared by the Supreme Court to be legal and Rani Anandbati Kumari, the legal heir and successor of the deceased Rani handed over the charge on the 10th May 1963. Kunwar Devendra Narayan Singh, son of late Anandbati Kumari, is a well known political leader and social worker of the region having won the Jarmundi assembly seat twice. Shri Dipnath Rai, brother-in-law of Kunwar Devendra, is the first Khetauri MLA of this region.

Manihari was inherited by Rupkaran's lineal descendant, Pratap Singh, followed by Mani Singh. The next descendant Kishori Singh embraced Islam and married a member of the family of Shah Shuja, but his nephews, enraged at his apostasy, assassinated him. Coming to later times, the raids of the Paharias (Malers) forced Sujjan Singh, to grant 36,000 bighas *jagirs* in order to prevent their incursions. However, after some of their chiefs were treacherously murdered, they stormed Lakrargarh and drove out the Khetauri *jagirdars*, challenging and ultimately destroying their status of being in military rank. Sujjan Singh was succeeded by his son Gajraj Singh who was succeeded by his two sons, Raja Bhagwan Singh and Kumar Chandan Singh. In

1838 *zamindari* of Manihari was sold for arrears of revenue and purchased for Rs 15,500.¹² Rani Dularbati, the wife of Bhagwan Singh and Musamat Kalabati, the wife of Chandan Singh, both lived till 1888 and were in receipt till then of Government pensions. During the resettlement operations of 1898-1910, Nahal Singh and Sib Narayan Singh, descendants of Mahtab Singh, a brother of Raja Gajraj Singh, were at the helm of affairs. Its last proprietor Roop Narayan Singh got killed by his younger son and the British government forfeited the property and pension was fixed for the family members.

The ruins of the forts at Barkop, Mahagama (Patsunda), Lagwa (Handwe) and Lakrargarh (Manihari) are testimony of the glorious past of the Khetauri kings. Nothing much is however, left of the Lakrargarh Fort. The other forts appear to be mostly single storey buildings, of medium size and having medieval features. Ruins of ancient *Kutcheries* could be seen at the Lakhan Pahari village near Barkop, at the Barkop village, at Mahagama headquarters, at the footsteps of Lagwa hill and at Nonihat headquarters. Judicial proceedings of the estates were conducted in these *Kutcheries*.

Remains of *Thakurbadis* could also be seen in these estates. Remains of *Laxmi-Narayan Mandirs* could be seen near the ruins of Patsunda Fort and Lagwa fort. They are traditional Hindu temples. Idols of Laxmi and Vishnu are kept in it. Khetauris worship Shakti in the form of *Durga, Kali, Bhagwati*, etc. Only symbolic stones or mounds of earth are kept in the *garb-griha*. Puja is generally performed through tantric method by the Khetauri priests. Animal-sacrifice is in practice. *Yogini Mandir* situated in the eastern side of Barkop village at the foothills of *Yogini Pahar* is among the famous *Shakti Peeths* of India. A temple dedicated to goddess Kali could be seen in the vicinity of the erstwhile Patsunda estate. An old temple of *Chanchala Devi* is established on the banks of Dhowriver, near the Lagwa fort. A prominent *Shiva Mandir*, also known as the Manokamna Mandir is situated on the top of *Dhansukh Pahar* at Barkop. Several temples of a later date could be seen in close vicinity of the erstwhile Patsunda estate. Chief among them are the temples of Lord *Shiva*, Goddess *Kali* and Seven Deities signifying *Sheetla Mata*.

From their early days Khetauris have a tradition of *Phagdol*. In the month of *Phalgun* on *Purnima*, Lord *Krishna* is swayed in a swing attached to the *Phagdol*. Remains of *Phagdols* could be seen at these estates. Elephants of the royal force were kept in *Hathi-Ghars* and their ruins could be seen adjacent to the forts. Besides, remains of

Shikargahs, Hammams, ancient Lakes and Ponds, etc. could be noticed.

Khetauris might have been simply a ruling lineage which gradually turned endogamous in Santhal Pargana. According to scanty historical and tradition based references, Khetauris are only known to have emerged from Kharagpur seat of power, who on being driven out by Rajput invaders worked hard to gain power in Santhal Pargana. However, it would be reductive to remember them for their ruling exploits only. It is clear that the Khetauris were one of the earliest settlers in the region and had established their *zamindari* suzerainty in a great part of Santhal Pargana. But gradually all their *jagirs* were lost and they came in direct fight, first. with the Rajputs adventurers, then with Malers causing their downfall. The Khetauris gradually lost political hegemony, social prominence and economic excellence that they had in the region. The successive downfall of the Khetauris also largely affected the social structure and economic life of the community.

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